

The Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on the Chromates of Hydrogen, Ammonium, Sodium and Potassium.

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This work continues the investigation of the reducing action of hydrogen sulphide on potassium and sodium chromates (Dunncliff and Soni, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 81), chromic acid (Dunncliff and Kotwani, *ibid.*, 1931, **35**, 3214) and potassium and sodium dichromate (Kotwani, Hamid and Dunncliff, *ibid.*, 1935, in the Press.)

Dunncliff and Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 505) have shown that, in certain circumstances, sulphite is formed in the precipitate and this confirms Dunncliff and his co-workers in the view that sulphite is the precursor of both sulphate and thiosulphate in this series of reactions.

It appears that oxygen (as chromic acid) and sulphur compete for the sulphite and that the proportions of thiosulphate and sulphate vary according to the conditions of the reaction, the sulphate being apparently completely suppressed in the presence of much alkali while both radicals appear when chromic acid is reduced.

Sulphite has never been detected in the reduction of hydrogen, ammonium, sodium or potassium chromates at any temperature whatever the concentration, even when air was very carefully excluded. All the work in the last paper (Y. S. potassium dichromate) was carried out at 19-20°. It is clear that if, by any chance, the reaction $(\text{SO}_3)'' + \text{O} \rightarrow (\text{SO}_4)''$ is more accelerated at higher temperatures than the reaction $(\text{SO}_3)'' + \text{S} \rightarrow (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)''$, sulphate might appear, even though only in small quantities, in the end-products.

Sulphate has never been detected among the reduction products of ammonium, sodium or potassium chromates at any temperature or concentration but, when ammonium or potassium dichromate was treated with hydrogen sulphide at 90-95°, air being carefully excluded, sulphate made its appearance. The results using methods of analysis and calculation previously described are shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

	Filtrate		Precipitate			Total	Total	Total
	(S ₂ O ₃).	(SO ₄).	(S ₂ O ₃)	(SO ₄).	S.	(S ₂ O ₃).	(SO ₄).	Cr ₂ O ₇ .
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	1.	9.96 g.	1.65 g.	1.90 g.	0.62 g.	16.55 g.	11.86 g.	2.27 g.
						50.69*	41.50*	9.27*
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	2.	10.26	1.59	1.86	0.65	16.14	12.12	2.24
						49.42*	42.42*	9.14*
(NH ₄) ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	1.	9.74	2.54	2.56	1.12	19.85	12.30	3.66
						52.11†	36.90†	12.81†
(NH ₄) ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	2.	10.12	2.48	2.38	1.26	19.54	12.50	3.74
						51.20†	37.50†	13.09†

* In terms of K₂Cr₂O₇.† In terms of (NH₄)₂Cr₂O₇.

These results suggest that a rise of temperature favours the formation of sulphate at the expense of thiosulphate. If this is so, the reduction of chromic acid at high temperatures should show an increase of sulphate at the expense of thiosulphate.

Comparative values found for reduction of chromic acid at 90-95° and at 20° are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

	(S ₂ O ₃)	(SO ₄)	Free S.	In terms of CrO ₃			Total.
				S ₂ O ₃ .	SO ₄ .	S.	
At 90-95°.							
1.	1.08 g.	27.24 g.	10.38 g.	2.56	75.66	21.62	99.84
2.	1.12	27.14	10.26	2.66	75.39	21.38	99.43
At 20°.							
3.	5.96	25.22	7.30	14.17	70.06	15.21	99.44

When hydrogen sulphide was passed through 50 c. c. of 5% K₂Cr₂O₇ at 90-95° for different intervals of time and the sulphate determined in the precipitates, it was shown that, when the brownish colour due to chromium dioxide has disappeared, no more sulphate is formed and the filtrate is alkaline. Duplicate results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Time (approx.).	Colour and reaction.	I		II	
		BaSO ₄ .	(SO ₄) calc.	BaSO ₄ .	(SO ₄) calc.
5 min.	Brown, acidic	0·0228 g.	0·0094 g.	0·0206 g.	0·0085 g.
10	Brownish green, almost neutral	0·0362	0·0149	0·0334	0·0138
15	Green, alkaline	0·0366	0·0146	0·0362	0·0149
30	Green, alkaline	0·0366	0·0151	0·0356	0·0146

These results confirm the view that the formation of sulphate is suppressed by an alkaline medium.

The Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Ammonium Chromate and Dichromate.

When ammonium dichromate was treated at ordinary temperatures in exactly the method described for potassium dichromate (*loc. cit.*), the filtrates presented no new feature of interest but the intermediate brown precipitate contained chromium dioxide and hydroxide, thiosulphate, one or more thionates, sulphide, ammonium, ammonia (adsorbed and co-ordinated) and free sulphur.

The final green precipitate contained chromium hydroxide, thiosulphate, sulphide, ammonia (adsorbed and co-ordinated) and free sulphur.

Part of the ammonia is removable by continued washing with warm water but the rest is not expelled until the precipitate is heated with concentrated potash. Similarly, sulphide cannot be completely removed by washing, the final residue requiring treatment with acid for complete elimination of sulphide.

Table IV, condensed from a much larger number of analyses, indicates a sudden rise in ammonia (column 3 + 4) at No 6 and sulphide at No. 4, which suggests ammine formation in the first case and, in the other, a compound containing co-ordinated hydrogen sulphide molecules—a new feature of particular interest although these chromium compounds are not capable of identification in so complicated a mixture.

TABLE IV.

Estimation of ammonia and sulphide.

Values correspond to 1 g. of ammonium dichromate.

No.	Vol. of H ₂ S-water used.	Co-ord. sulphide in ppt.	Co-ord. NH ₃ in ppt.	NH ₃ in filtrate.	Total NH ₃ (Theory = 0·1349 g.).
1	30 c. c.	Absent	0·0063	0·1286	0·1349
2	50	Absent	0·0060	0·1280	0·1340
3	70	0·0032	0·0062	0·1271	0·1333
4	90	0·0032	0·0116	0·1220	0·1336
5	110	0·0072	0·0116	0·1230	0·1346
6	170	0·0307	0·0119	0·1229	0·1348
7	210	0·0313	0·0116	0·1218	0·1334
8	250	0·0492	0·0118	0·1216	0·1334

The reaction has to be carried out with full precautions against the loss of ammonia, of which both the filtrate and the precipitate smell strongly. The values in the last column show that this has been achieved.

Table Va shows the values for components in the filtrate with increasing amounts of aqueous hydrogen sulphide and Table Vb, the corresponding analyses for the precipitates at each stage.

TABLE Va.

Filtrate.

Values are shown for 1 g. of ammonium dichromate.

No.	Colour and reaction.	Vol. of H ₂ S soln. used.	CrO ₄ in terms of (NH ₄) ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	Thionate in terms of SO ₄ .	Thiosulphate (S ₂ O ₃).
1	Brown, acid	30 c.c.	0·6353 g.	0·0677 g.	0·0251 g.
2	Brown, neutral	40	0·5060	0·1179	0·0584
3	Light green, alkaline	50	0·3150	0·1419	0·0769
4	" "	60	0·3037	0·1437	0·0917
5	" "	70	0·2633	0·1422	0·1004
6	" "	80	0·2234	0·1179	0·0892
7	" "	90	0·1286	0·1075	0·0832
8	" "	100	0·1254	0·0543	0·0776
9	Green, alkaline	110	0·1246	0·0540	0·0749
10	" "	130	0·1196	0·0530	0·0567
11	" "	150	0·1063	0·0141	0·0505
12	" "	170	0·0643	0·0084	0·0482
13	" "	190	Absent	Absent	0·0391
14	" "	210	"	"	0·0371

TABLE Vb.

Precipitate.

Values are shown for 1 g. of ammonium dichromate.

Expt. No.	Chromate in terms of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.	Cr_2O_3 .	Corresponding $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.	Thionate in terms of (SO_4) .	(S_2O_3) .	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in the ppt.
1	0.0822 g.	0.1560 g.	0.2586 g.	0.0107 g.	0.0371 g.	0.3408 g.
2	0.0863	0.2472	0.3898	0.0387	0.0860	0.4760
3	0.1224	0.3092	0.5126	0.0314	0.0923	0.6350
4	0.1048	0.3418	0.5667	0.0302	0.1001	0.6715
5	0.0746	0.3862	0.6404	0.0193	0.1094	0.7150
6	0.0722	0.4064	0.5738	0.0135	0.1084	0.7460
7	0.0684	0.4762	0.7893	0.0101	0.1092	0.8577
8	0.0426	0.4929	0.8167	0.0063	0.1083	0.8593
9	0.0184	0.5023	0.8328	0.0064	0.1074	0.8512
10	Absent	0.5224	0.8661	Absent	0.1054	0.8661
11	„	0.5286	0.8764	„	0.1044	0.8764
12	„	0.5246	0.9264	„	0.1026	0.9264
13	„	0.6022	0.9984	„	0.1103	0.9984
14	„	0.6013	0.9969	„	0.1109	0.9969

TABLE Vc.

Expt. No.	Total $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in ppt. & filtrate.	Total tetra-thionate in terms of SO_4 in ppt. & filtrate.	Total S_2O_3 in ppt. & filtrate.	Expt. No.	Total $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in ppt. & filtrate.	Total tetra-thionate in terms of SO_4 in ppt. & filtrate.	Total S_2O_3 in ppt. & filtrate.
1	0.9761 g	0.1084 g.	0.0822 g.	8	0.9847 g.	0.0611 g.	0.1859 g.
2	0.9820	0.1566	0.1444	9	0.9758	0.0604	0.1823
3	0.9801	0.1733	0.1642	10	0.9857	0.0530	0.1621
4	0.9752	0.1739	0.1918	11	0.9827	0.0141	0.1549
5	0.9793	0.1615	0.2098	12	0.9907	0.0084	0.1508
6	0.9744	0.1314	0.1976	13	0.9984	Absent	0.1494
7	0.9863	0.1176	0.1924	14	0.9969	„	0.1480

Table Vc shows that tetrathionate, formed in the side reaction,

increases to a maximum (No. 4) and is then progressively decomposed by hydrogen sulphide to complete elimination. Thiosulphate increases with the alkalinity in the filtrate to a maximum (No. 5) and is then progressively decomposed to a constant value. The thiosulphate in the precipitate increases to a constant maximum value as expected, no loss being observed *pari passu* with the reduction of concentration of thiosulphate in the filtrate.

This is peculiar to the reaction under consideration and is due to the fact that easily hydrolysable ammonium thiosulphate is decomposed by hydrogen sulphide. In an actual experiment at ordinary temperature, 90% of a 0.2% solution of ammonium thiosulphate was decomposed by passing hydrogen sulphide through it for 5 hours (15-18°).

The transitory presence of tetrathionate as a bye-product was shown, as described in the case of potassium dichromate (*loc. cit.*), by oxidising the filtrate and precipitate with bromine water. By the same method, the absence of tetrathionate from the final product was also established.

It has been proved that potassium trithionate (method of Mackenzie and Marshal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1732) is not decomposed by hydrogen sulphide and should, therefore, appear in the end-products of that reaction if formed at any stage. There is no thionate present in the final products of the reduction of potassium dichromate by hydrogen sulphide and therefore it is inferred that trithionate is not an intermediate or bye-product in the action of hydrogen sulphide on ammonium dichromate though, like the thiosulphate, ammonium trithionate would be decomposed by hydrogen sulphide.

The action of hydrogen sulphide on ammonium chromate gives similar products, including the intermediate formation of a little tetrathionate which is eliminated in the completed reaction.